

Australian Research Data Commons

Cross-NCRIS EOI FAQs Register

FAQs Register

To ask a question please fill in the online form.

Reponses to questions will be made within 3 business days of submission.

Question

Answer

1	What are expected project sizes?	We expect projects up to 800 k\$. Please note that this means ARDC will invest up to 400 k\$, which with the 1:1 co-investment will get to 800k\$.
2	What are expected project durations?	Projects can be up to a maximum of 2 years.
3	What are the expectations on the co-investments?	A 1:1 co-investment is required, this amount can be divied between the partners in a project.
4	What is the expected outcome?	Core deliverables of this program are the enhanced data assets themselves, including multi-party governance and collaborative arrangements needed to sustain them.
5	How many NCRIS facilities should partner in a project?	Projects should include at least 2 NCRIS facilities as project partners.
6	Can the data be provided from 1 NCRIS facility?	No, the data asset must include data from at least 2 NCRIS facilities.
7	Is this program limited to NCRIS facilities?	No, other organizations can make submissions as long as 2 NCRIS facilities are partners in this project.
8	What is an NCRIS facility?	We use the list of funded research infrastructure projects from https://www.education.gov.au/funded-research-infrastructure-projects
9	Can ARDC be one of the partners so that it would count as one of the 2 NCRIS facilities?	No, ARDC does not count within the minimum of two. The objective of the program is to support cross-facility data assets. ARDC does not have its own data.

10	How much is this about the data itself? Can it be used to build a platform to bring this type of data together?	A balance between platform and data will be important. Actually bringing some datasets together from facilities is an essential ingredient; equally important is an extensible data infrastructure platform to allow the capability to maintain and expand content in the future. Together data content and data platform will make a strong data asset. ARDC has another program called "Platforms" that invests in the development of platforms or virtual research environments into which research tools can be deployed. Projects whose major focus is on the development of such an analytic platform or processing pipeline would be better suited to ARDC Platforms program.
11	Can the data asset be relevant to two NCRIS facilities but data would be from only one NCRIS facility?	No, we need data from two NCRIS facilities in this program.
12	Must co-investment be cash? What constitutes eligible co-investment?	No, it does not have to be cash. At least an equivalent level of co-investment (1:1) to ARDC funding, over the total period of the project. Co-investment must be in an auditable form (in accordance with reporting and accountability requirements as specified by the Commonwealth Department of Education) and can be cash (from project partners or other grants), investment from other NCRIS Projects, or effort/labour. NOTE: if contributing effort/labour, work on the project must be a significant amount of the person's time, i.e. 25% or more).
13	Is it ok if one of the two NCRIS partners is not funded through NCRIS anymore?	<u>The official list of NCRIS facilities is here.</u> Previously funded NCRIS initiatives are in scope.
14	is it ok if a non-NCRIS facility provides large amounts of the data, since they are not an NCRIS facility?	Having a non-NCRIS facility to also contribute would make the project more valuable and not all integrating parties need to be NCRIS. However, data from 2 NCRIS facilities is necessary.